

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: WRIGHT****FIRST NAME: JENNY****PROGRAM CODE: LLM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: P1****INSTRUCTOR: PR. LAURENT CLEENEWERCK****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical).

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references.

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access).

The author used the following software: MS Word 2016 on Windows 10.

ESSENTIAL CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The required course materials for this period included various tips, guidelines, and instructions on the essential concepts of academic writing. While I am confident many students were previously familiar with most of the content, I appreciate the pedagogical approach of ensuring all students are clear on what is expected of them before proceeding any further on the program. This is a great way to manage expectations and ensure everyone is on the same page from the beginning. When I commenced my first graduate degree, I was surprised how inexperienced many of my fellow students were in terms of academic writing. I would argue that the high dropout rate within the first few months of the program could have been avoided if better preparation and training had been offered initially.

Managing expectations is not only part of preparing new students before embarking upon their studies, but is an equally important part of effective academic writing. After all, the primary objective is to “persuade readers of an idea based on evidence.” It is important to promptly lay the foundation for what the reader should expect by clearly presenting your argument and supporting evidence (EUCLID 2015, 2).

In this paper, I will argue that effective academic writing is best achieved by remembering the three first letters of the alphabet: A (for *accuracy*) B (for *balance*) and C (for *consistency*). Regardless of the complexity or academic level of the research topic, I believe the key to writing a well-developed academic paper, or research report, is by adhering to these three key words throughout the writing process.

2) **THE ABC'S OF ACADEMIC WRITING**

Writing academic papers can sometimes feel daunting. It might be difficult to know where to start, but it is important to remember that academic writing is not a “linear process” (EUCLID 2015, 2). As you discover new information, draw new conclusions, or adjust your perspective, the nature and structure of the paper will evolve as well.

It is, however, important to have a basic roadmap before you commence to ensure you do not stray too far from the original research question and remain focused. One roadmap, which has served me well in the past, is to adhere to the following three key concepts: accuracy, balance and consistency.

a) Accuracy

The first step of academic writing is to decide what question you intend to research and how you will conduct your research. Clearly defining the research question, specifying why further research is needed on that topic, and clarifying the scope and limitations of the research is essential to ensuring the results are accurate and relevant. Defining what you intend to research and how you intend to approach the study is a critical starting point before planning your next steps (EUCLID 2015, 2).

A thorough literature review of all relevant sources on the research topic is also necessary to ensure accuracy. After all, academic writing “draws on the work of other writers and researchers.” It is always good to build on what you already know, and make a plan from there on what additional reading is needed to be able to answer the research question (EUCLID 2015, 3). Personally, I prefer to do some introductory readings first to determine what prior research has covered and what are commonly accepted theories and deductions within my focus area. Secondly, I do a cursory search for various sources on the topic and skim through for any relevant information. I save the sources with information I wish to review more closely, while I discard the sources that lack any useful information. Once I have completed this initial screening, I return to the saved sources and do a more in-depth review of each while compiling notes and references of from which source I found each piece of information.

It is also important to write clearly and straight “to the point” (EUCLID 2015, 43). A famous quote frequently attributed to Albert Einstein is: “If you can’t explain it simply, you don’t understand it well enough.” While this is sound advice to all researchers, particularly in terms of academic writing, the attribution itself is an empirical example of the importance of source criticism. According to Justia (2018), critically assessing and evaluating the validity, credibility (including possible ulterior motives) and timeliness (considering whether the information is still applicable and relevant) of a source is essential when selecting what to include, or exclude, in academic writing. For example, in the case of the quote, some open source research promptly revealed that it is debatable whether Einstein ever said or wrote this in the first place. Do not believe everything you read.

Proper attribution is essential not only to give credit to the academic work upon which the research is based on, but also in order to avoid plagiarism. Put simply, plagiarism is the act of passing someone else's words or other content off as your own. Whether intentional or not, plagiarizing is not only unethical and punishable, but a severe academic *faux pas* that puts the researcher's professionalism and integrity into question. Plagiarism is easily avoided by properly citing any information, thoughts or evidence retrieved from someone else (EUCLID 2015, 10-13).

b) Balance

The second key concept to keep in mind to ensure effective academic writing is balance. It is important to remain as impartial as possible throughout the process. Valid research should be possible to replicate using the same methodology, regardless of who the researcher is, and so forth. Including or excluding sources, theories, samples or evidence without good cause might give the impression the research is biased, which will discredit the validity of the results.

It should be noted that the choice of research topic is, from the start, subject to bias as it is influenced by the inherent interests and values of the researcher (Westmarland 2001). While challenging, the researcher should strive for balance and value-neutrality even in the initial phase of defining the research question and focus (Weber 1949). Fortunately, researcher bias does not imply that the research itself is biased (Game & Metcalfe 1996; McNeill & Chapman 2005). To avoid bias, it is important to provide a balanced and unbiased account of all the relevant evidence and solutions of a research question as possible.

Fairly representing different perspectives, especially those that differ to your own, shows the underlying research was thorough and could even strengthen your own arguments if presented effectively. Disagreeing with another researcher is permissible, but should be done professionally and under the assumption the other researcher did properly consider and review their argument and/or evidence before publishing it and respect their conclusion, even if it differs from your own (EUCLID 2015, 44).

c) Consistency

There are endless ways to present, style and format an academic paper. The key to a professional looking result and effectively presenting your arguments is consistency. Regardless if you are writing the paper yourself or one of many authors, the structure, format and language must remain the same throughout the paper. Lack of consistency distracts the reader from the content of the paper, and instead puts the quality of the work and knowledge of the researcher into question.

Proper planning, including developing and revising an essay plan, is vital to ensure consistency throughout the process (from defining to answering the research question). A good starting point is to develop a thesis statement, which describes the

research topic as well as the argument and evidence you aim to highlight (EUCLID 2015, 1-3). The thesis statement provides a foundation for the “red thread” that should flow through the paper to guide the reader through your reasoning. It is best to refrain from being too general or vague, particularly in the thesis statement and in the conclusion, as it lacks academic value, and might leave the reader with an impression that the author is either inflating their results or does not fully comprehend the subject or its implications (EUCLID 2015, 43).

Spelling and grammar should also remain consistent. American and British English are both acceptable spellings, but cannot not be used interchangeably. Select one type of spelling and grammar and maintain those rules throughout the paper.

As far as sentence structure, the required readings (EUCLID 2015, 43) offered the following recommendations worth considering:

If a sentence occupies more than (say) 5 lines, find a way to divide it up; if a paragraph goes on for more than 20 lines, find a way to divide it up; if your paper falls into sections, make sure to include a sentence or two of connective tissue between the sections.

According to the required readings (EUCLID 2015, 40), longer papers should separate the content into sections with clearly descriptive headings to create a “logical flow” for the reader. I agree with this advice, but would also recommend creating basic mind maps or listing key words or concepts under each headline before you start writing complete paragraphs. This approach enabled me to visualize how I would organize the information, like pieces of a puzzle, in a logical sequence before I even started writing the paper. Furthermore, it mitigates the risk of duplicating or overlooking information once you are ready to write the first draft. Finally, draft and revise the draft multiple times before finalizing the report.

3) CONCLUSION

The required readings included a wealth of information on how to develop your research question, plan your study, conduct your research, structure your writing and properly attribute credit to the sources you used. In this paper, I categorized the content into three key concepts based on the main points I derived from the readings: *accuracy*, *balance* and *consistency*.

Accuracy is vital to ensure the validity of the research by clearly defining the relevant research topic before commencing your research, and sufficiently reviewing available literature to make an accurate deduction based on your findings.

Balance is important to ensure value-neutrality and prevent the risk of bias. All views should be presented professionally, regardless of the researcher’s own personally views. Relevant information, evidence or samples should not be excluded without good cause, just as irrelevant information, evidence or samples should not be included without cause.

Consistency must be maintained throughout the process to ensure there is a clear structure and methodology applied as basis for your results. Adhering to a “red thread” throughout the text enables the reader to follow your reasoning and, ideally, reach the same deductions you did in your study. It increased the likelihood of you convincing the reader your argument is valid, relevant and unbiased.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.
<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed April 7, 2019).

Justia. 2018. *How To Evaluate Information – Checklist*. Virtual Chase.
<https://virtualchase.justia.com/how-evaluate-information-checklist/> (accessed April 17, 2019).

Westmarland, Nicole. 2001. The Quantitative/Qualitative Debate: A Subjective View of Objectivity. *Forum: Qualitative Social Research* 2, no. 1 (February 2001),
<http://www.qualitative-research.net/index.php/fqs/article/view/974/2124>
(accessed April 11, 2019).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.